

Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance in Unilever Nigeria PLC, Agbara Ogun State

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ABSTRACT

This study is anchored on uncovering the relevance of motivation in the relationship to management of human resource, unprogram fits snugly without it and no company achieves its mission without influencing one's means. Ultimate aim of motivation is often toward arouse individuals to bring out member of staff courageous diligence into achieving organization goals with enthusiasm and productivity. Particularly, this research look at the motivation for effective and as well as efficient service provision. The study emphasized on the relevance of motivation as a crucial determining factor for performance of employees within a corporate entity either public or private. The study adopted a expressive research survey which served as its blueprint, upon which the empirical investigation was done. The population size of this particular study underpins a number of mid-level employees in Unilever Nigeria PLC, who are about one hundred (100). A total number of sixty (60) considered selected from this population using stratified sampling technique and data was generated using questionnaires. Data was analyzed electronically with the aid of the social science statistical kit, on which the three hypotheses were tested through Correlation and Variance Analysis. The results of the findings showed that motivation justified having an effect on employee productivity despite its association with organizational efficiency and employee turnover. This study affirmed that human-management skills and creativity maybe enhance when employees personal freedom encouraged, moment as well as other significant resources needed.

KEYWORDS: *Employee, Human-Management, Motivation, Organization, Performance, Productivity, Reward*

1. INRODUCTION

The fast paced growth or value decline of any organization either private or public depends on its employee. This is an outcome of how well all employees are motivated towards their work looking at the amount of commitment they put in motion (Adelenwa, 2013). Employee determination plays an indispensable role in improving an organization's efficiency and results. Mullins (2015) stressed that engagement, efficiency and competitiveness of the employees may additionally be substantially linked. An institution must understand that employees are its greatest asset; therefore, they should be able to easily identify those employees who are highly productive and the ones who needs training. Kashmala and Faiza (2015) argue that each staff member has its own motivational determinants which inspire them to proactively complete their tasks. Several employees are motivated by acknowledgment as well as some by rewards. In a nutshell, organizations are supposed to be mindful of the needs of their workers. Inspired employees are efficient, satisfied, executed and accomplished for their work (Kashmala&Faiza 2015).

Chukwuma, Maduka&Obiefuna (2014) indicated that managers would motivate them to work towards a common goal by inspiring the employees. This principle also helps employees become more productive and allows for improvement and transformation. An individual often has the motivation and determination to achieve something or a certain objective but lacks the drive, commitment and

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willingness to act (Quratul, 2012). This is due to absence of encouragement. Furthermore, Quratul (2012) affirmed that motivation endorses engagement, increases initiatives gives focus, energy and commitment to institutional priorities. According to Azar&Shafighi (2013), a encouraged personnel takes motion and does something it wants to reap organizational objectives, urged that motivation is one in every of factors that structure success depend on. When the motivation is low, or the organization recocrding only poor outputs, but incorporation of motivational acts, there is tendency for organization receives greater and better results and accomplishments (Kashmala&Faiza, 2015). Deficiency of motivation shows a lack of passion and determination, while motivational supports is a image of empowerment, high interest and a preparedness to try whatever it takes to to attain what the company needs achieved (Nduro, 2012). Sometimes employee is aware of how to work properly so that the operation is perfectly coordinated, while options are available, but he prefers not to do it for one purpose or another, which usually means that it is a motivational problem, family, conflicts due to personality traits (Quratul, 2012, Adelenwa, 2013).

Employees are the well-being of a company, how they sense about a assignment they do, and the results of that work have an effect on the accomplishment of company stability directly (Quratul, 2012). For an illustration, staff members of institute remain motivated extremely and initiative oriented,

may willingly do whatever is obligated to attain the organization's objectives and retain track of the performance of an association to handle any unforeseen concerns (Jishi, 2009).

Furthermore, bi-dimensional method could be adopted to maintain stability of the staffers and productivity. An organisation with poorly motivated workers is completely vulnerable to internal and external threats, as its employees may not become redundant to keep the company in balance (Jishi, 2009).

1.1. Research Problem

Management function seems more complex, especially in large labour-intensive organizations. With the initiation of the competition, there is an increased necessity for personnel managers to look for a system to assist in managing employees extra effectively (Jishi, 2009). The concept of motivation has provided some essential apparatuses in this area in the recent years.

Although, companies face the idea of having the right personnel to represent themselves in their work with delicacy and efficiency, companies ignoring use of motivation as a factor to enhance productivity because of lack of knowledge or misunderstanding of how it would be implemented. Some of the justifications that can be related to this condition are indeed lack of trained workers to expand actual recommended strategy, the lack of upper-management support and hesitation in a very venture as it can be perceived as expense rather than benefit by management. The government's approach towards encouraging private sector involvement throughout the economy will create a lot of institutional awareness-regulation and a revival focus to its wake. Many of these organizations are infatuated with complicated hiring and selection criteria, seeking the greatest workforce and obtaining the first and most advanced equipment to achieve comparative advantages (Nurun&Monirul et al, 2017). The manager should be able to inspire staff to do likewise. But that's easier said than done, because a business with low motivational opportunities may be forced to experience a high turnover of labor.

Despite the previous applied research recommendations, the topic of motivation seems indistinguishably understood and the conducted ones are often than not poorly. An understanding the criterions for motivation of employees and so efficient management and leadership expected to improve production of the company. Although seeking ways to motivate workers could be a difficult option among companies, However it is a vital part of any effective undertaking. Employees may have higher results as employees feel more encouraged. Essentially, if workers are really productive the all-inclusive company will reap the produce of hard work

1.2. Research Objective

The main objective of this study is to assess the effect of motivation on employee performance. The precise intentions are to:

- To observe the nature of relationship between motivation and morale of employees
- Assessing the relationship between motivation and productivity in organizations.

1.3. Research Question

In reference to the mentioned concerns, the study aims to suggest the following answers:

- Does motivation has any relationship with employee performance?
- Would there be any meaningful relationship between employee morale and motivation?
- Is there any meaningful link between motivation and organizational efficiency towards turnover rates?

1.4. Research Hypothesis.

Ho₁; Motivation has no relationship with employee performance

Ho₂; There is no meaningful relationship between employee morale and motivation

Ho₃; There is no link between motivation and organizational efficiency towards turnover rates

1.5. Scope of the study

This particular study initiated at Unilever Nigeria PLC, Agbara Ogun State, study focused on the organisation's five (5) departments. The survey was carried out on staff within these departments.

2. Literature Review

According to Chaudhary & Sharma (2012), motivation may be a term derived from 'motive'. The sense of "motive" is the person's desires, interests, and desire. Employee motivation thus means the mechanism in which the company encourages its workers to accomplish corporate goals in the form of incentives, promotions, etc.

Nurun&Monirul et al, (2017) defines motivation as a psychological human trait which leads to the extent of dedication of the participant. It refers to achieving a goal, indicated by a target-directed behavior. If we refer to anyone being motivated, we suggest that a certain mission is being undertaken by the person.

Motivation is the highest position enhancing sources and helping human nature (Mullins, 2015). Motivation is the level of willingness of an organism to attain some intended goal, and implies the determination of the existence and locus of forces that induce the extent of willingness in the interpretation of the management encyclopedia.

Motivation is a mechanism by which action needs to be instigated to expectations that can meet those needs (Jones & George, 2017).

If staff consider their opinions to be respected, they are supported with an adherence intelligence which can inspire employees. The incentive always fulfills the demands and specifications of the workers, and by hard work and honesty the individual people claim it back. The organization's purpose is to categorize needs, desires and respond to the most basic method of obtaining worker engagement from all organizations (Surbhi, 2012).

Seth (2003) retorted that motivation is an internal process that enables a person to move towards a certain objective. Rockson (2005) affirmed that a person's drive to do something is motivation. The study affirmed that motivation bring about a goal-driven action that is guided and sustained. Bright (2000) defined a company's motivation and indicated that it could be said that motivation was about willing to do

with encouragement."Buchanan (2010) believed that motivation is a situation-making mechanism via which person selects the desired results and sets into motion the action that is important to them. Buchanan (2010) described motivations as discovered human nature influences leading to specific goals being pursued, because they are valued. Therefore, motivation can be seen as the extent to which an individual wants to and chooses to engage in certain behaviours.

2.1. Notable Motivational Types: Intrinsic and Extrinsic

A closer review on various motivation theories demonstrates that two main types of motivation exist: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Internally motivated actions are found where there is no other noticeable incentive besides the action itself (Surhbi, 2015). Malone and Lepper (2017) described it as what people would do without outside induction. Sources of intrinsic motivation include hunger, a sense of duty, altruism and the urge to be valued. Extrinsic motivated actions are the ones where the mechanism of influence is clearly visible (Surhbi, 2015). Cash, rules and laws, and the physical environment are examples of extrinsic motivation.

Malone and Lepper (2017) observed that internal motivated behaviors are common and can lead to creativity, versatility and spontaneity, whereas externally motivated behaviors are typically exerted as a result of pressure, resulting in low self-esteem and fear. The debate also centered on a simple definition of internal and external behavior (Scott, 2015), despite this, due to mutual influence, the fundamental difference in internal and external motivation is considered important.

Much research was done on the effects on one another of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, especially in the field of education. Several scholars find learning is intrinsically unsatisfactory (Larson, 2014; Cameron and Pierce, 2014), and that extrinsic motivation has the opposite effect than desired on student achievement (Malone and Lepper, 2017).

Cameron and Pierce (2014) claimed that validation, such as award, would not automatically harm motivation, managers must be mindful that staff could do more harm than good by simply spread over extrinsic motivation methods without addressing intrinsic factors to augment. Executives in charge need to comprehend that they are actually propagating a undesirable cycle of constant compensation and intrinsically diminishing motivated by simply rewarding workers by extrinsic means.

2.2. Types of Strategies for Motivation

To a definite extent, effective management strategies create a high level of worker motivation. Jishi (2009) emphasized that the motivated development of employees requires the manager to treat people as individuals, enrich employees, include an effective remuneration system, re-plan jobs and create an adaptable workplace; The strategies are listed and considered as subheadings in the next paragraph.

➤ Employee Empowerment Strategy

Empowerment happens when freedom, authority and inspiration are given to people in an organization to carry out a mission. Empowerment is intended to free the worker

and render active employee responsibility. Managers promote intrapreneurship in industry in an effort to empower and change some of the outdated bureaucratic practices. The intrapreneur motivates leaders always explore new ideas and encourages those ideas to be put forward by staff. Apparently intra-entrepreneurship is not for the weak of heart, because it rehabilitates old structures and processes (Fielding, 2006).

➤ Provision of Dependable Reward System

Occasionally managers use rewards to encourage the behaviour of the staff they wish to continue with. A reward is the consequence of an individual's work that has positive value. Organizations give unstinting rewards to staff who are helping toward achieve the organisational goals through performance successes. The rewards people are receiving in one of two ways:

- **Extrinsic rewards**, are valued results given to someone by another person, usually a supervisor or manager of higher level. Extrinsic rewards could be paid out in bonuses, promotions, unusual tasks, office equipment, honours, public recognition, etc. are typical workplaces. In every situation, the motivational inducement of extrinsic rewards emerges external concern of the individual (Fielding, 2006).
- **Intrinsic rewards** are self-administered, think about the natural high level a person may experience after completed a job. The person feels good, because they have a sense of integrity, personal development, and self-control in their work. In comparison to extrinsic rewards, the motivational reinforcement of intrinsic rewards is internal and does not depend on the actions of others (Fielding 2006).

Jobs re-designing

Most people go every day to work and take the same, unenthusiastic acts to perform their jobs. Some people often refer to that disorder as a burnout. Before a worker becomes frustrated or even begins to lose justification, however, smart managers can do something to change this. The philosophy of job restructuring, which requires an understanding or appreciation of the human characteristics that people bring to the company, incorporates motivational strategies into the work environment to improve productivity and contentment. Managers take into account both the scope of work and the intensity of employment while restructuring jobs. Tents to redesign may include:

- **Job enlargement**: Also denoted to as *horizontal work-loading*, career expansion expands the range of responsibilities included in a work (Fielding, 2016). Even if the quality or difficulty of such tasks does not improve, the expansion of the work will reduce part of the monotony, and as the dissatisfaction of an employee decreases, the quality of his or her job is in general improving.
- **Job rotation**: This method assigns, on a temporary basis, different people to different jobs or activities. The suggested goal is to increase diversity as well as depiction people to another employment that one employee has. Job rotation will foster higher performance indicators and revive interest and optimism. The entire business profits from a well-groom workforce.

➤ **Job enrichment:** Also known as vertical work preparing, this requirement not only involves range of responsibilities on the other hand gives an employee extra accountability plus authority. If a skill required to do the job were skills which suit the jobholder's expertise, job enhancement could increase optimism as well as efficiency (Fielding, 2016).

Creating Flexibility

Employees now value personal time because of family needs, a typical nine-to-five working day might not suit many people. Flextime, which allows workers to set and manage their own working hours, is, therefore, one way that companies meet the needs of their employees. Here are a few other choices which organisations are also trying:

A compressed workweek; it is a type of flex time enabling the completion of a permanent job in less than the normal forty-hour, five-day workweek. The utmost common form of the schedule is 4/40, which gives workers three days off each week. The most common type of scheduling is 4/40, giving workers three days off every week. The user benefit from this package by providing extra leisureliness time as well as some expenses. More absenteeism and better performance will help the company. Though, the concern of such scheduling is obviously the likelihood of increased fatigue (Fielding, 2006).

Twinning or job sharing: This exists as you split one full time job in the middle of numbers of above people more than two. Job allocation frequently includes each employee that works one-half a day, but may also be done on plans for 5-7 days or four weeks sharing. If jobs can be separated and transferred, employers will benefit from hiring talented people who otherwise would not be able to work full time. The professional worker who is a parent may not want to spend a full day at work, but should be prepared for a duration of half a day. While adaptation complications always exist, the method can be ideal for everyone concerned (Fielding, 2016).

2.3. Employee Performance

Landy's research (1985) and numerous other study on employee productivity which indicated that if individuals are satisfied with their jobs, this will result in higher work performance and hence greater job discharge than those who are not satisfied with their work. It was also claimed that employees are more likely to leave their jobs if they are not satisfied and less willing to perform better. The performance of highly satisfied and happy workers is higher so the organization can easily accomplish its target goals and objectives through the participation of this higher employee. Individual performance in the field of human resource management is all about employee performance at an entity or organization. For the success of the organization or the employee, making every single effort to support small performers is very important. But if the organization is unable to successfully empower its employees, then it is very challenging for a company to exit in the competitive business climate (Ahmad, 2012).

In addition, Ahmad (2012) affirmed five categories of performance. Plan, grow, analyze, control as well as reward. Number one stage is planning, planning involves creating strategy and setting goals to achieve the objectives.

Monitoring is the continuous calculation and presentation of employee response and collection of effort on their improvement towards the achievement of their goals. The worker is imaginative in the developing stage in order to increase any reduced performance that has been seen over the time. This move is intended to reward and distinguish excellent conduct like that which is better than probable. Employee performance is ultimately affected by ability, organizational environment, and motivation. Without employee involvement creativity can not be instituted (Liu, C.H, 2013 Ottenbacher & Harrington, 2007).

Motivation influences the efficiency of individuals in the company by supplying or giving various kinds of opportunities and rewards. Individual performance is deliberated as what a worker does, and what they do not. Individual performance requires the quantity and quality of productivity, mixing commitment, and outcome timeliness. Individual performance is essentially prejudiced by enthusiasm as if workers are fulfilled or driven by more effort than they will, and in the long run improve enactment (Azar & Shafiqhi, 2013).

Rewards and incentives are key to transforming the discontent into enjoyment for the employees. Mehmod (2013) also notes in his study that if employees are satisfied they will be doing the job with more motivation and the desire to do better would lead to good results. Motivated employees are more concerned with self-sufficiency than low-motivated workers, and more self-driven. Motivated workers are genuinely well motivated to perform well on credit (Kuvaas & Dysvik, 2009). Acceptable salaries or wages play a vital role in improving the performance of the worker as well as enhancing the productivity of an organization. Individual performance is a mixture of behaviors workers display in relations to their jobs (Rashidpoor, 2000 Hakala, 2008).

2.4. Ways to Measure Employee Performance

Performance evaluation has become a continuous process by which an employee's perception of the goals of an organization and its progress in contributing to them is assessed (Ajagbe et al., 2014). Measuring performance is a continuing task for the managers and co-workers, performance assessment uses and measures the following performance indicators:

Quantity: a respectable target output measured in number of units produced, processed or sold.

Quality: the quality of the work done can be calculated using different methods. The metric is based on the percentage of the work output to be redone or removed (Ajagbe et al., 2014)

Timeliness: how quickly work gets done is another success metric that can be used with caution. Constant downtime for the consumer in field service is a strong indicator of timeliness.

Cost effectiveness/efficiency: the cost of labor performed could also be used as a performance metric if the employee has some cost control.

Managers appraisal: Manager assesses efficiency of the employee and passes the assessment to the employee.

Appraisal of managers is done by definition top-down and does not really promote a constructive engagement of employees. Resistance is often found, because the employee always feeling development is impossible.

Self-evaluation: the employee reviews his or her own results, contrasting in many cases the self-evaluation with assessment of the management. Self-evaluations can indeed illustrate differences between what the employee and management believe are relevant performance factors and provide shared input on concrete expectations change.

Team appraisal: related to peer appraisal within this team members who may hold different positions are asked to evaluate the performance and working styles of each other. This strategy assumes clear definition of the goals of the team and the planned commitment of each participant (Hakala, 2008).

2.5. Theory and Framework of the Study

To provide a clearer view of the subject, Douglas McGregor's proposed theory X as well as Y adopted in this current study. Douglas McGregor is an American social psychologist who in his 1960 book 'The Human Side of Enterprise' developed this popular X - Y principle with which to interpret employee motivation theory X as well Y are still made reference to as a prevalent academic acknowledgment in the field of management and motivation, and while some minority probed the rigor of the model his theory stands as a valid fundamental root for developing optimistic management modus operandi. These two philosophies instigate with the premise that management's job is to aggregate the factors of production, including individuals, to the pecuniary advantage of the company, McGregor (1960).

McGregor, Theory X suggests the typical creature:

- A. Displeasures work as well love to evade the involvement
- B. Lack determination, dislike obligati or responsibility, and rather obey rather than lead.
- C. His self-seeking, then carefree in term of organization's goal.
- D. Counterattacks change.
- E. Is deluded, and not especially smart.

Theory X assumption is that people only for keeping the job.

McGregor Y-theory

Continuous needs are the higher-level expectations of esteem and self-actualisation, in that they are never fulfilled. It is those desires with higher level as such, that can help

inspire staff. Hence the theory makes broad statements as follows:

- A. Work and playmight be as usual productive
- B. People will be nature-directed if they are committed to achieving their job objective.
- C. If there are incentives in hand might content higher needs such as self nirvana, publics might be dedicated to their goals.
- D. Under these conditions, people will pursueobligation.
- E. For the reason thatin the group imagination and cleverness are common, most people can tolerate responsibility.

Under these theories, personal objectives can be matched with corporate objectives by using the worker's own desire for contentment as main motivator. McGregor underlined that management of the theory Y not connote a soft methodology. His study admitted that some employees may not have achieved the maturity level implied by Theory Y and may hence entail close-fitting controls which might be relaxed as the employee grows.

3. Research Design

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of motivation on employee productivity in Unilever Nigeria PLC. Several studies justified that quatitative research captures quality reasults (Solomon, et al., 2013; Solomon et al., 2016; Oluwagbemiga et al, 2019, Oluwagbemiga et al., 2018a). Investigating attitude of group of people, quantitative study affirmed (Oluwagbemiga, et al., 2017a; Solomon & Endozo, 2019). The design adopted quantitative research method and sample consists of all over one thousand (1000) employees in the organization. The researcher strictly focused on FIVE (5) stratified groups with the aid of stratified sampling technique. The sample was randomly chosen based on the groups which are A, B, C, D, E. From each stratum, twelve (12) employees were selected for the study. On the whole, a total of sixty (60) employees served as subjects in the study. The study used the Statistical Pack (SPSS) to scrutinize collected data and with specific electronic means (Villanueva et al., 2019; Santos, 2017; Oluyinka et al., 2018). Hypothesis well stated maybe used to justify research significance of a study (Oluwagbemiga et al., 2017b; Oluwagbemiga et al., 2018b; Endozo, 2019). Thus, three hypotheses were tested through Correlation and Variance Analysis

4. Data Analysis

H₀: Motivation has no relationship with employee performance
 This SPSS 21 data analysis was carried out at 5% level of significance.

Correlations			
		Motivation	Employee-performance
Motivation	Pearson-Correlation	1	.830
	Sig@ two-tailed		.000
	N	42	42
Employee performance	Pearson-Correlation	.830	1
	Sig@ two-tailed	.000	
	N	42	42

SCATTER PLOT

Motivation and employee performance correlation hypothesized was significant, $r(42) = .830$, " is interpreted as a very strong association between motivation and employee performance with $p(0.000) < .001$ indicating a statistical significant association between the two variable leading to rejecting the null stated hypothesis (Motivation has no relationship with employee performance) to accept the alternative hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis Two

H_0 : Motivation and employee productivity has no relationship.

P-value less than 0. 05 significance considered in justifying approval or rejection of the study’s findings. The model extracted from the validated data using SPSS 21 is defined below:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \epsilon$$

Where;

β_0 - noted as constant or intercept

x_1 - Described ad the *Independent variable motivation*

Y - Employee productivity connote *Dependent variable*

ϵ - component *error*

$$\text{Employee performance} = 0.529 + 0.210x_1$$

Where, independent variable is motivation

x_1 = motivation

This could be translated as a unit rise in motivational effect contributes to an increase of 0.210 in employee productivity.

Summary of the Model				
Model	R	R-square	*Adjusted R-square	Standardized Error/stimate
1	.771 ^a	.594	.601	.02617
A. Predictors-Constant),motivation				

Table 1 summary of the model, noted adjusted R-square has moderate fit with (0.601). The table suggested that constructed simple regression model of the (motivation) as the independent variable account for just about 60% variance in the dependent variable (employee productivity). Adjusted R square and standard error of the estimate mention about the performance of model, however, standardized error of the estimate 0.02617 showed that the model is dependable since is almost upto zero. (ii) The coefficient is equal to $r=0.771$, this specified a robust positive link between the motivation and employee productivity. The findings for the framework on the variance analysis included in Table 2.

*ANOVA ^b						
	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean-Square	F	Sig@
1	*Regression	.962	1	.962	18.797	.000 ^a
	Residual	2.200	40	.051		
	Total	3.161	41			
A. Predictors-Constant, motivation -as IV						
B. Employee-productivity as the D-Variable:						

The findings of the variance analysis, F (df 1, 40 = 18.79, P < 0.05), showed a statistical significance effect of the motivation on the productivity of employees. The estimatet for the β value, sum of standard deviation unit difference in the dependent variable was determined on the basis of this important relation. The findings are as shown in below table 3.

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized-Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	β	Std. Error	β			
1	(Constant)	.529	.078		4.461	.000*
	Motivation	.210	.039	.552	4.336	.000*
A. Employee productivity stands as D-Variable:						

Table 3's standard-coefficients show that:

The independent variable, motivation factor contribution has a strong positive impact on the productivity of workers because the standardized β-coefficient (0.552, 0.000) indicating statistically significant contribution to the benefit is less than 0.05.

Third Hypothesis reports

H₀: There is no significant relationship between motivation and employee turnover

Using SPSS 17 to run the data's chi square test, the following was obtained at 0.05 This analysis was performed on significance point. The model using SPSS 21 derived from the analysed data is described below.

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \epsilon$$

Where;

β₀ - Connote constant

X₁ - Independent variable motivation

Y - Dependent variable employee v

ε - Is the error component

Employee turnover = 0.529 + 0.210x₁

Therefore, x₁ = motivation

This is interpreted as a unit increase in the impact of motivation leads to 0.210 increases in employee v.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R-square	Adjusted R-square	Standardized Error of the Estimate
1	.771 ^a	.594	.601	.02617
A. . Constant as Motivation/Predictors:				

There is reasonable fit from the result in table 1, modified R-square (0.601). It shows that in the dependent variable (employee turnover) constructed simple regression model of the independent variables (motivation) accounts for about 60% variance. Adjusted R² and standard error of the estimate mentioned performance of model, however, standard error of the estimate 0.02617 indicated supported. (ii) The relationship estimate (r=0.771) indicated a strong positive association between the motivation and employee turnover. The results presented in the Table 2

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig@.
1	Regression	.962	1	.962	18.797	.000 ^a
	Residual	2.200	40	.051		
	Total	3.161	41			
A. Constant- Predictors: (IV-motivation)						
B. Employee turnover as D-Variable:						

The outcomes, F (df 1, 40 = 18.79, P < .05), specified supported, coefficient for the β on the sum of standard deviation unit shift in the DV was determined on the basis of this important relation. The findings are as shown in below table 3.

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.529	.078		4.461	.000
	Motivation	.210	.039	.552	4.336	.000
Dependent Variable: Employee turnover						

Table 3 justified that suggested independent variable, contribution of motivation value has strong positive effect on

employee turnover because the standardized coefficient β-value (0.55, .00).

5. Research Conclusion

The impact of motivation in the day-to-day achievement of the employees cannot be over-emphasized, particularly with regard to being recognized for a job done. It is a well-known fact that by through motivation human output of any kind is enhanced. It can be easily concluded from the findings of this study that staff motivation matters a lot and should be a concern of both the employer and the employee. The results obtained from the hypotheses showed that employees place great value on the different forms of motivation given to them by their employer. Therefore, when there is no encouragement, workers tend to express their dissatisfaction through poor performance and non-commitment to their job which can lead to turnover of employees. It is therefore necessary for companies to recognize and not just ignore the needs and feelings of their workers in order to safeguard workplace peace, since "they say a satisfied worker is a productive worker." As the effects of good motivation on employee performance and the different types of motivating strategy that can empower workers to perform better on a job have been lauded, this research can, therefore, be seen as an appeal to the employer's sense of commitment to put in place the right reward package that will encourage employees to be more purposeful and develop their jobs.

6. Recommendation

Employers are constantly challenged to establish a motivating strategy to attract, inspire, retain and please their workers. This study's findings can be a handy tool that could be used to provide solutions to individual disputes arising from weak motivation. Thus, suggested recommendations;

1. Management can encourage innovation by providing workers with the opportunity, time and other tools. Management should be telling them regularly what they need to improve their innovative thinking and productivity. Of passion and support, this act must be carried out.
2. Organizations must provide input on results of the workers to provide clear feedback. It provides the means to inspire the staff to the desired behaviour. Through keeping them updated, one assists in removing some of the anxiety and keeping them focused on what needs to be done.
3. Some of the common factors that motivate an employee at work are opportunities that take care of employee motivation such as pay, benefits, good working climate, gratitude, healthy environment. Therefore, management expected to include all workers in brainstorming issues affecting a company in order to find the most suitable one for each employee. Once everyone is interested in finding the right motivational plan, it is predicted that everyone will be inspired to engage in decision-making and thus promote teamwork, which will increase productivity.

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